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CIPP Evaluation Model for Vocational Education: A Critical Review

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Abstract

The CIPP model has been widely used in the evaluation of vocational education. However, there has been no research that examines the suitability of CIPP in evaluating vocational education. Therefore, this study examined the suitability of CIPP in evaluating vocational education through a literature review. This research was a literature review using the narrative review method. Based on the results and discussion, it was concluded that the CIPP model could provide a real picture of the conditions that occur in programs implemented in vocational education and could be the basis for providing recommendations for solutions given to the constraints found in the four dimensions contained in the models. However, weaknesses were found in the evaluators who had not been able to provide in-depth analysis of the problems that needed to be improved and given solutions so that the evaluation stage was still on the surface of the program being implemented. As a recommendation, it was suggested that the implementation of evaluation activities could not only be emphasized on the model used but also on who was doing the evaluation (evaluator) and the accuracy of the program with the subject that was used as a source of information in determining the success of a program.

Keywords: CIPP, Evaluation, Vocational Education

1. Introduction

Vocational education is education that prioritizes mastery of vital skills to meet the needs of skilled workers in Indonesia. Vocational, according to Airlangga Hartanto, Coordinating Minister for Economic Affairs, plays an important role in Indonesia's progress in the future (FER, 2022). In fact, in 2022, the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology established the Directorate General of Vocational Education to improve the quality of vocational education in Indonesia. To maintain the quality of education, including vocational education, it is necessary to evaluate its implementation. Evaluation is different from assessment although it uses the results of the assessment. Evaluation is a systematic effort to collect information to make judgments or decisions (Lynch, 1996), on one or more service programs (Hadley & Mitchell, 1995). Evaluation is not carried out once but is an

activity carried out within a certain period of time (United Nations Development Programme, 2002) to obtain an accountable report (Stufflebeam, 2000).

In conducting the evaluation, several models have been developed by experts, including the objective model (Tyler, 2013), responsive model (Stake, 1983), Goal Free model (Scriven, 1991), and Context, Input, Process, and Product (CIPP.) models (Stufflebeam, 2000). All of these models have been developed and used mainly in the field of educational evaluation, especially the evaluation of educational programs. Among all these models, CIPP is one of the oldest models and has been thoroughly tested. This model was developed in the United States for the first time in school programs and then applied in various fields such as social programs, business, military, health, education, etc. (Stufflebeam, 2000). The CIPP model has four distinct dimensions: context evaluation, input evaluation, process evaluation, and product evaluation. Context evaluation is concerned with assessing needs, problems, and opportunities in a defined environment. Input evaluation is used to evaluate competitive strategies, work plans, and budgets for the chosen strategy to implement the program or project. Process evaluation is used to monitor and assess the activities carried out during program implementation. And, product evaluation helps identify and evaluate desired or undesirable short-term, long-term program outcomes (Stufflebeam, 2000). Process evaluation is used to monitor and assess the activities carried out during program implementation. And, product evaluation helps identify and evaluate desired or undesirable short-term, long-term program outcomes (Stufflebeam, 2000). Process evaluation is used to monitor and assess the activities carried out during program implementation. And, product evaluation helps identify and evaluate desired or undesirable short-term, long-term program outcomes (Stufflebeam, 2000).

The CIPP model has been widely used in the evaluation of vocational education, including those related to the teaching factory (Pratiwi et al., 2019; Qolik & Marsono, 2021; Supriyantoko et al., 2020), competency certification programs (Budiyanto & Suyanto, 2020; Irwanti & Sudira, 2014; Suwarno & Ismanto, 2020); work practices or industrial internships (Ardiani, 2020; Mardiyah & Supriyadi, 2013; Samidjo, 2017), and special programs carried out in vocational education (Salam & Soenarto, 2013; Sunnah & Sukoco, 2014). Despite the fact that the CIPP model is necessary to show the discrepancy of the program being evaluated (e.g. Sa'adah et al., 2017; Surawan & Andriani, 2022; Winarni et al., 2014); however, until now there has been no research that examines the suitability of CIPP in evaluating vocational education. Therefore, this study aims to examine the suitability of CIPP in evaluating vocational education through a literature review.

2. Method

This research is a literature review using the narrative review method. A narrative review is a type of review that is useful in gathering a large amount of literature in a particular subject area and synthesizing it. The aim is to provide the reader with a comprehensive picture, identify and describe an issue of current interest, and understand the knowledge or highlight the importance of the new research (Demiris, Oliver, & Washington, 2019; Paré & Kitsiou, 2016). The steps in conducting a narrative review are conducting searches, identifying keywords, reviewing the contents of abstracts and articles, as well as summarizing and synthesizing findings from articles, and integrating them into writing (Demiris et al., 2019). The articles used as study material are national and international articles, for the last 10 years, related to the CIPP evaluation model for vocational education in Indonesia. Articles that discuss vocational education in Indonesia, but do not use the CIPP model, are not included as review material.

3. Results

According to the formal law in Indonesia (Undang-Undang Nomor 20 Tahun 2003), Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills needed by themselves, society, nation, and country. The meaning of education can simply be interpreted as a human effort to foster his personality by the values of society and culture. Thus, however simple the civilization of society, in it occurs or takes place as an educational process. That's why it is often stated that education has existed throughout human civilization. Education is essentially a human effort to preserve his life.

Ki Hajar Dewantara defines education as an effort to advance the character, mind, and body of children so that they can advance the perfection of life and bring children to live in harmony with nature and society. It's just that the notion of education is still general, while the development of conditions requires educational programs that are ready to use and ready to work, both working independently and working in certain industries known as vocational education.

Vocational comes from the Latin "vocare" which means to be called, summons, command (summon), or invitation. According to Billet (2011) "vocations are products of individuals experiences and interests, that are, in some ways, a person dependent.constrain the human capacities required to undertake those activities". Vocational is an interesting product or service and is a person's personal experience that causes other people to depend on or need it so that they are called or invited to do a job.

Rupert Evans (1978) for example, defines vocational education as part of the education system that prepares a person to be better able to work in one workgroup or one field of work than in other fields of work. This definition implies that every field of study in vocational education as long as the field of study is studied more deeply than other fields of study and the depth is intended as a provision to enter the world of work. Thus, English is studied more deeply than others for work purposes, so English is vocational education. Clark & Winch (2008) mention that "vocational education is confined to preparing young people and adults for working life, a process often regarded as of rather technical and practical nature."

Discussing the output or output of higher education, it is known that there are still many higher education alumni who experience a mismatch between education and work. According to the Minister of Manpower for the 2014-2019 Working Cabinet, Muhammad Hanif Dhakiri, only about 37% of the workforce worked according to the study program they took during the study period. The rest, which is 63% of the workforce, does not work according to the diploma they received (Mardiana, 2017). The mismatch here means that regardless of ability and choice of study program taken during the lecture period, the selection of work undertaken after becoming a workforce (outcome at the company) is not in line.

Head of the Vocational Education Program, University of Indonesia, Sigit Pranowo said, so far the award for vocational graduates is still low, both from SMK and Diploma. Generally, at every recruitment, the person who is looking for is always a graduate. Moreover, in CPNS registration opportunities for vocational graduates are still rare. "This happens because there is no harmonious communication between labor providers and users," said Sigit. Since the 90s, the government has launched a link and match between vocational education and industry. However, the preparation of the curriculum is still running independently. Education providers feel able to see the needs of the industry. Meanwhile, the industry feels that vocational education graduates are not ready to work. Therefore, the involvement of the industry is essential so that vocational graduates meet the standards of needs, for example, through practical activities involving instructors from the industry. (Revitalization of Vocational Education in Indonesia, 30 July 2020)

Based on the problems encountered, it is known that learning, especially in vocational education, both in SMK and in diploma programs, has not been fulfilled or has not been able to bridge the needs of industry with the abilities of students developed in vocational education. It has also been conveyed, that there is a lack of integration between the industry as a stakeholder and schools or campuses as product providers, in this case, the output of workers who are ready to use in the industry.

The obstacle may also be that the needs of the industry are so broad and continue to grow, while the vocational learning program is not up to date. The provision of programs in the form of a curriculum is one solution, wherein the preparation and evaluation of the curriculum are necessary to have representatives from the industry who convey the programs and trends they are programmed for so that learning programs can be able to follow. It was emphasized that the integration of industry programs as stakeholders with campuses or schools in the form of a learning curriculum, only able to follow, cannot fully match with industry so that to be more connected, a follow-up program is needed in the form of Work-Based Learning (WBL) or Workplace-Based Teaching and Learning (PBTk) as a further policy solution. WBL is a learning approach that utilizes the workplace to structure experiences

gained in the workplace to contribute to the social, academic, and career development of learners and to supplement learning activities. The learning experience in the workplace is applied, refined, and expanded in learning both on campus and in the workplace. With WBL, learners develop attitudes, knowledge, skills, insight, behavior, habits, and associations from experiences in both places and allow learning to occur. related to real-life work activities (Lynch & Harnish, 1998).

Education is a long-term investment, as an investment from an economic perspective, education is a form of commodity. This means that there is an economic value when the mastery of knowledge, skills, and expertise produced and possessed by individuals can be returned within a certain period through types of work in line with the competencies obtained during education.

Although there are various definitions, the essence of the formulation remains the same. The Joint Committee on Standards for Educational Evaluation defines the term evaluation as a systematic investigation activity to determine the value and benefits of the object being evaluated. Fitzpatrick revealed that evaluation is a process of identifying, classifying, and determining criteria to determine the value (worth or merit) of objects that are evaluated based on these criteria (Fitzpatrick, 2011).

Various evaluation models are usually carried out, depending on the understanding and objectives to be achieved and the evaluator's point of view in conducting the evaluation. One of the evaluation models for the implementation of education, the CIPP evaluation model can be used. The CIPP evaluation model consists of four evaluation components, namely context, input, process, and product. By adhering to regulations, the evaluator can formulate the object that is the evaluation target for each component of the CIPP evaluation model.

Data collection techniques, data analysis techniques, determination of evaluation criteria, and decision targets cannot be separated from the CIPP component including from stakeholders, it's just how the evaluator packs it into a determinant in the evaluation results. As stated by Stufflebeam that the determination of criteria depends on the point of view of the evaluator and mutual agreement between the evaluator and stakeholders (Stufflebeam, 1985)

The CIPP evaluation model was developed by Daniel Stufflebeam in 1966. Stufflebeam stated that the CIPP evaluation model is a comprehensive evaluation model that has formative and summative functions. The formative function of evaluation is to provide information to improve and develop the program while the summative function of evaluation is to consider to determine the success or continuation of the program (Stufflebeam & Coryn, 2014). CIPP consists of four evaluation components, namely context evaluation, input evaluation, process evaluation, and product evaluation. The four components of this evaluation are a complete series. This is why the CIPP evaluation model is referred to as a comprehensive evaluation model.

Context evaluation starts from the question what is needed? The purpose of context evaluation is to find out the strengths and weaknesses of the evaluator (Stufflebeam, 1983). Information regarding strengths and weaknesses will determine the actions that can be taken. The next component in the CIPP evaluation model is the input evaluation. Evaluation of inputs helps regulate decisions related to plans and strategies to achieve goals. The focus of the input evaluation study includes a) human resources, b) supporting facilities and equipment, c) funds/budget, and d) various procedures and rules required (Widoyoko, 2014). Process evaluation is carried out to monitor, collect information and prepare reports on the implementation of program planning. This evaluation provides feedback or input to stakeholders to assess the progress of the program. Stakeholders can use the information from this evaluation to find out whether there are deficiencies in program implementation, both strategy and program achievements (Stufflebeam & Coryn, 2014). The final evaluation component in the CIPP evaluation model is product evaluation. In this component, the evaluator identifies the results of program implementation, both short-term and long-term results. This evaluation measures the success of the program based on the objectives that have been set. The results of the product evaluation will be input for stakeholders to determine the sustainability of the program (Widoyoko, 2014).

Although the four evaluation components are declared to be a unified whole so that a comprehensive evaluation model is declared, Stufflebeam also conveys that in its implementation the evaluator can use one or a combination of two or more evaluation components (Stufflebeam, 1983). Because each component in the CIPP evaluation consists of a different focus of study, namely: 1) assessing goals and priorities by comparing them with available needs, problems, and opportunities; 2) assessing the implementation plan and the required budget by comparing it with the targeted goals, 3) assessing the effectiveness of the program, 4) assessing the success of the program by comparing the results and side effects with the targeted needs, checking its cost effectiveness, and (possibly) comparing costs and outcomes with competitive programs; also by interpreting the results that hinder the expenditure of resource efforts and the extent to which operational plans are well and effectively implemented (Stufflebeam & Coryn, 2014).

4. Discussion

The CIPP model has been widely used in Indonesia to find a solution to the underlying problem of the imbalance between the needs of the Business World and the Industrial World and Vocational Education in terms of providing competent resources in their respective fields. The government's policy is Link & Match or can be interpreted as a match between the needs of industry and graduates of vocational education which in its implementation has various obstacles or problems in practice. The CIPP model is used as a tool to determine whether there are obstacles in the implementation of a program starting from the context, input, process, and product to be able to provide practical solutions on how a program should be maintained, repaired, or, for example, discontinued.

According to the Minister of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia, Nadiem Makarim, current vocational education cannot meet industry needs. He said that vocational education providers are still plagued with several problems, starting from the curriculum, and the quality of graduate workers, students, and teachers. Previously, the Minister of Manpower, Ida Fauziyah, said that the domestic vocational education model was still problematic. This is reflected in the open unemployment rate (TPT) in Indonesia, which is still dominated by SMK graduates. Referring to open unemployment data released by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), the TPT figure reached 13.55 percent. This shows that there is no link and match between vocational education and the labor market. This problem is a challenge for all vocational schools in Indonesia to find a solution to the question of how a program should be run to be able to realize the Link & Policy. Those matches. When examined in depth, each school has characteristics and limitations in implementing each program carried out such as human resources, curriculum, as well as facilities, and infrastructure, which may be far from the ideal conditions for a program to be implemented properly. The suitability between the evaluation model used and the program that is trying to be evaluated will determine whether the recommendations given are appropriate or even vice versa, namely creating new problems that are far from the main purpose of the evaluation activity itself.

One program that might be able to support the link & match policy is an industrial work practice program or fieldwork practice where this program is one of the schools' efforts to create a match between learning activities in schools and real conditions in the industry. With the CIPP evaluation model, the evaluator seeks to see how far this program can be run and, in its implementation, it is described from the four dimensions of this evaluation model, namely context, input, process, and product. In evaluating a program there is a goal that must be used as a reference so that errors do not occur. A good evaluation must be detailed and accountable in its implementation. In the evaluation, it should meet the conditions that are used as a reference so that it is right on target.

Wisanti (2016) conducted a study at the Islamic Vocational High School Bustanul Ulum Pakusari Jember which was intended to determine the level of suitability of the on-the-job training program implementation in terms of Context, Input, Process, and Product. The results of the evaluation can be used as information to determine the follow-up of the program being implemented. The evaluation of the on-the-job training implementation in this study uses the CIPP evaluation model, which is to see the on-the-job training implementation from Context, Input, Process, and Product. This evaluation assessment standard is compiled in a research rubric adopted from various foundations regarding the implementation of on-the-job training. The results of this study indicate that in general the implementation of on-the-job training at SMK IBU Pakusari has been carried out in accordance with the procedures set by the government, but still needs improvements in the system to run optimally. Based on the

context evaluation, it is necessary to adjust the objectives of the on-the-job training implementation with the curriculum used and the need to analyze the achievement of competency learning outcomes in schools as the basis for student activities during on-the-job training. Based on the input evaluation, it is necessary to provide teaching materials/materials in the implementation of on-the-job training activities following the needs of the school and the provision of normative and adaptive teaching materials in the form of modules that are given as long as on-the-job training participants carry out on-the-job training activities. Based on the process evaluation, shows that technically the implementation process has gone well, however, several obstacles must be a concern for the IBU Pakusari Vocational School so that the implementation of the next on-the-job training would be better, including difficulties related to the material obtained at school, which should also be a concern for the future. Meanwhile, based on product evaluation, the value obtained by on-the-job training participants is satisfactory, which is above the KKM determined by the school.

Prastoyo and Sulistyono (2020) seek to determine the achievement of the implementation of Overseas Industrial Practices at the Faculty of Engineering, Yogyakarta State University in 2018 in terms of Context Evaluation, Input Evaluation, Process Evaluation, and Product Evaluation. The results of the evaluation show that (1) The achievement of context evaluation is included in the very good category of 87.5% with 28 respondents and an average total score of 12.5. (2) The achievement of input evaluation is included in the very good category of 90.63% with 29 respondents and an average total score of 80.7. (3) The achievement of the process evaluation is included in the very good category of 75% with 24 respondents and an average score of 131.5. (4) The achievement of product evaluation includes aspects of achievement with the aim of industrial practice included in the very good category 81,

Ardiani and Ridwan (2020) conducted a study that aims to describe the context, input, process, and product of the industrial work practice program at SMK Negeri 6 Bungo. This research is evaluation research with the CIPP model. The methodology used is a combination method (Mixed Methods) with a Sequential Explanatory design. Based on data analysis, it was found that the level of achievement of the internship program in the context variable of the internship program at SMK Negeri 6 Bungo was 93.99% with a very good category. The input variable for the internship program at SMK Negeri 6 Bungo is 91.52% with a very good category. The variable process of the internship program at SMK Negeri 6 Bungo is 97.62% with a very good category. The product variable for the internship program at SMK Negeri 6 Bungo is 78.80% with a good category. The internship program's objectives at SMK Negeri 6 Bungo have not been fully achieved, the implementation strategy and the procedure for placing students in the internship schedule have been carried out according to the procedures, and communication with DU/DI has been improved. Cooperation with industry needs to be improved.

Several other research results, including Aferi, and Waskito (2019), discuss the evaluation of the implementation of industrial work practices in class XI TKPI at SMK Negeri 10 Padang using the CIPP method where this study aims to evaluate the internship program from the Context, Input, Process, Evaluation fields. Areli et al (2020) evaluated the on-the-job training program which showed that there were positive implications for the implementation of on-the-job training had carried out their duties well, through various stages of activities ranging from preparation, debriefing, implementation process, and evaluation monitoring. Overall, the implementation of the internship has been going well. The curriculum is appropriate and applied to student Internship activities so that the implementation of the internship runs smoothly, efficiently, and effectively.

From some of the research above, the CIPP model is able to provide a real picture of how the conditions that occur in the internship program and possible solutions are given to the constraints found in the four dimensions contained in the model. However, weaknesses can be found in the evaluators who have not been able to provide an in-depth analysis of the problems that need to be corrected and given solutions so that the evaluation stage is still on the surface of the program being implemented.

The implementation of evaluation activities can not only be emphasized on the model used but also on who is doing the evaluation (evaluator) and the accuracy of the program with the subject that is used as a source of information in determining the success of a program. The CIPP model is comprehensive and is quite easy to use but requires a deeper understanding of the program to be evaluated so that it is truly able to find the critical point

of the four dimensions used in the evaluation process. Furthermore, it would be very wise if the evaluation was not only carried out once but was carried out continuously on a program that had been given recommendations so that what were the improvement points were implemented and the results could then be seen in real terms.

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